

Law on Communication Technology and Pornographic Items: Nigeria Perspectives

Simeon Olaosebikan Oni

Faculty of Law

Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

simeonolaoni@gmail.com +234 807 455 9030

Abstract

Pornography is defined as the act of using materials to initiate, design, expose, circulate, introduce, advertise or promote indecent items, especially material depicting children engaged in sexual acts with adults. The term “pornography” can be used in discussion and debate to refer broadly to material that is sexually designed primarily to produce sexual arousal in viewers, or to material that is sexually harmful to women and children. It is defined in the Black's Law Dictionary, as material (such as writings, photographs, or movies) depicting sexual activity or erotic behavior in a way that is designed to arouse sexual excitement. *This article examines the impact of pornography on the children, the youth, the unlawful use of pornographic materials by the adult as well as the Nigerian extant law that regulates this menace that unbalances the social equilibrium that disorganizes the national psyche.*

Keyword: Communication Technology, Pornography, Nigeria, Criminal Code, Penal Code, Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, Etc) Act

Introduction

According to the Concise Oxford Dictionary, it reads that obscene publication is anything repulsive, filthy, loathsome, indecent and lawn. In the same vein, Webster Dictionary also defined obscenity as offensive to morality or decency causing uncontrolled sexual desires, abominable, disgusting, and repulsive.

1 Black's Law Dictionary, Eighth Edition at page 1349, 2014.

2 Concise Oxford Dictionary, 2014 Ed.

The English Obscene Publications Act states that:

...an article shall be deemed if its effects or (where the article comprises two or more distinct items) the effect of any of its items is, if taken as a whole, such as to tend to deprave and corrupt persons who are likely, having regard to all the relevant circumstances, to read, see or hear the matter contained or embodied in it.

An indecent publication may be defined as a communication to another person (be it by distribution or projection, printing, making or manufacturing for distribution or projection) of any article which, having regard to all relevant circumstances, has a tendency to corrupt persons who are likely, to read, see or hear it. This definition also applies to an 'obscene publication', except that the corrupting tendency here is much stronger than that required for an indecent publication.

In *R. v. Stanley*, Lord Parker, C. J. held that

The words "indecent" or "obscene" convey one idea, namely, offending against the recognised standards of propriety, indecent being at the lower end of the scale... As it seems to this Court, an indecent article is not necessarily obscene, whereas an obscene article almost certainly must be indecent' Thus where a material is declared not to be obscene, it can still be held to be indecent.

The difficulty in defining obscenity predates 1868 when the English case *Regina v. Hicklin* was decided by the Queen Bench. For decades, the leading definition of obscenity, implemented in both state and federal statutes, came from Regina's case, where the court defined obscene materials with a "tendency . . . to deprave and corrupt those whose minds are open to such immoral influences."

While explaining the meaning and the attendant harm that obscene materials can cause, Kalven stated that there were at least four possible harms: "(1) the incitement to antisocial sexual conduct; (2) psychological excitement resulting from sexual imagery, (3) the arousing of feelings of disgust and revulsion; and (4) the advocacy of improper sexual values.

In this regard, while obscene material is defined as that which the average person would feel appeals to prurient interests, that it describes sexual actions in an obviously offensive manner, and that it has no serious literary, artistic, political or scientific value, indecent materials have contents that are patently offensive that is not quite at the level of obscenity.

3 Section 1 of the English Obscene Publications Act of 1959

4 Adeyemi, A. A. "Obscene and Indecent Publications." In: T. O. Elias (Ed.). *Nigerian Press Law*. Edinburgh: University of Lagos and Evans Brothers Limited, 1969.

5 [1965] 1 All E.R. 1035, pp. 1038-1039

6 *Regina v. Hicklin* [1868] L.R. 3 QB 360 at 371 (Eng.)

Obscene and indecent materials are mostly obtained through communication technology such as camcorders, polaroid camera, Cable television, smart speakers, social media platforms, wearable technology, premium telephone services, podcasts, computers, blogs, conferencing technology and websites (the internet) have become the foremost means for the circulations of child pornography in the last few decades. In the 1970's and 1980's, criminals who engaged in the acts of child pornography were seriously in danger as it was a subject that was anathema to the society and abhorred by law. During that time, the production and commercialization of child pornography was not easy to come by because of the societal perception of such materials. Hence, the materials were not only costly but hard to obtain. Attempt to transact on child pornography movie demanded a possibility of grievous risks which are no more there today. Previously, pornography industries lack the ability to create cinematography because of the exorbitant cost, hence, but now, video camera has changed the scene and child pornography has gone virile on the internet that even skit makers use underage children to promote their businesses via online accessibility.

The anti-pornography movement caused by the ready availability of pornography on the Internet is growing very fast. The movement includes critics who object to pornography on the traditional bases: that it injures the moral tone of society, corrupts immature minds, and leads to rape and other sexual crimes. It also includes the newer arguments of feminists that pornography furthers the subordination of women because pornography does not only treats women as objects and commodities for the viewer's use, it also teaches girls they are to be used and teaches boys to be users and that pornography treats women and children as objects and often depicts rape and abuse as if they are harmless.

Pornography in the United Kingdom Context

According to Itzin, the effects of pornography can be categorized into four. They are as follows:

- i. *Threat to Person:* Women and young girls cannot have a healthy self-image of themselves when their husbands and fathers look at pornography. It is an evil addiction. It is dehumanizing. It leads to increased incidence of rape. It can lead to increased incidence of HIV and AIDS. It usually comes with drug addiction. It has

7 Harry Kalven, Jr., *The Metaphysics of the Law of Obscenity*, SUP. CT. REV. 1, 5, 1960.

8 Gerard V. Bradley, *Prolegomenon on Pornography*, 41 HARV. J.L. & PUB. POL'Y 447, 447-56, 484-96 (2018).

9 Utah S. Concurrent Resolution on the Public Health Crisis, S.C.R. 9, 2016 Gen. Sess, 2016.

10 *ibid*

11 Itzin, C. *Pornography Classified*, 2003. <https://www.peacefire.org/censorware> (Accessed on 15th June, 2023).

led to an increase in home breakages. It can create a chain reaction leading to violence and other moral & societal decay. Children are being sexually molested by those looking for sexual gratification.

- ii. *Legal Threats*: Employees can sue if organizations don't provide a work environment free of gender & minority harassment. That means taking reasonable care to block offensive content.
- iii. *Network Threats*: An employee can crash the computer network just by logging into the wrong website.
- iv. *Security Threats*: Many viruses enter networks through web-based porno-content. Kidnapping is on the increase by those wanting to have it by all means with their acclaimed sex models.

Critics like Professor Gail Dines a leading feminist critic and proponent of the new public health arguments claim that the ubiquity of Internet pornography has “pornified” our culture and “hijacked our sexuality.” She and others point to research suggesting that pornography is negatively affecting sexual relationships, as viewers expect sex partners to submit to degrading and even violent sex acts they have viewed. In other cases, men have not been able to enjoy healthy sexual relations with women, as real sex partners cannot compete with those online. Other men have substituted watching pornography for sex with real women altogether. Women report having less sex, and less satisfying sex, with their partners. It gets worse. Critics cite psychological harms from watching too much pornography. Some claim that watching pornography actually physically alters the brain and can even lead to an addiction to pornography.

12 Longe, O. B., & Longe, F. A. (2003). Health Risks Associated With IT Applications. Proceedings of the 14th Annual Conference of the Nigerian Computer Society.

13 Gail Dines, *Pornland: How Porn Has Hijacked Our Sexuality*, (2010).

14 Nat'l Ctr. on Sexual Exploitation, Pornography & Public Health: Research Summary 1, http://endsexualexploitation.org/wp-content/uploads/NCOSE_Pornography-PublicHealth_ResearchSummary_8-2_17_FINAL-with-logo.pdf, 2017.

15 Ronald Weitzer, *Pornography's Effects: The Need for Solid Evidence*, 17 *Violence Against Women*, 667–75, 2011.

16 Ronald Weitzer, *Opinion, This Look at Porn Was Biased*, Wash. Post, 2016. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/opinions/this-look-at-porn-was-biased/>.

17 *ibid*

18 Matthew LaPlante, *In Utah, The Fight Against Porn Is Increasingly Being Framed as a Public Health Crisis*, Wash. Post, 2018, <https://www.washingtonpost.com/national/in-utah-the-fight-against-pornis-increasingly-being-framed-as-a-public-health-crisis/>.

19 Amber Phillips, *Porn Has Been Declared a 'Public Health Crisis' in Utah. Here's Why*. Wash. Post 2016. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/the-fix/wp/2016/04/22/anti-porn-advocates-are-changing-the-game-and-it-starts-with-utah-declaring-it-a-public-health-crisis/>.

The new anti-pornography social scientists claim that pornography actually reduces sexual violence, as it provides a release for harmful impulses. Others point out that critics miss the entire point of pornography, which is ultimately “about fantasy, boundary crossing and exploration of all that lies outside of the charmed circle of good old-fashioned vanilla, heterosexual sex,” according to Professor Miller-Young. She also challenges the methodology of the studies behind the claims relied on by Professor Dines and other critics, asserting that “they make problematic assumptions about what constitutes violence, agency and consensual pleasure in pornography” and “often obscure proper methodologies for selecting an accurate sampling across the myriad porn sub-genres and modes of production.” These new anti-pornography advocates urge a variety of remedies. An obvious one is further research and study on the use and effects of Internet pornography and the policy issues it raises. Some remedies are educational: proper sex education, which is sadly lacking in many school systems and homes; information about possible harmful effects of Internet pornography on healthy relationships between men and women; and on the possibility of psychological harms from, and even addiction to, pornography on the Internet.

Pornography in the Nigerian Context

The law protecting audience of mass communication from obscene and indecent publication has been enacted in many countries and Nigeria is not an exemption. The **lack of consensus over the definition** of obscene and indecent materials contributes largely to societal difficulty in determining the prevalence of pornography. It is clear, however, that **pornographic material is more easily accessible** now than in the past, **mainly because communication and information through technology has created new avenue through internet for downloading, exchanging and distributing such material. This practice presents unique challenges for the enforcement and prosecution of law related to pornography, since crimes committed over the internet are often envisioned as being borderless.**

20 Melinda Wenner Moyer, *The Sunny Side of Smut*, SCI. AM. 2011, <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/the-sunny-side-of-smut/>

21 Mireille Miller-Young, *Porn Isn't a Public Health Hazard. It's a Scapegoat.*, Wash. Post, pp67-89 2016. <http://www.washingtonpost.com/news/in-theory>

22 Ronald Weitzer, *Opinion, This Look at Porn Was Biased*, Wash. Post 2016. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/opinions/this-look-at-porn-was-biased>

23 Rubén de Alarcón et al., *Online Porn Addiction: What We Know and What We Don't—A Systematic Review*, J. CLINICAL MED., 15 Jan. 2019, at 1, 11–12.

24 Miller-Young *supra* p.78

25 NAT'L CTR. ON SEXUAL EXPLOITATION, *supra* note 7, at 11.

26 *ibid*

Notwithstanding the uncertainties of definition, many believe that material that depicts violence or that demeans women is demonstrably harmful and should be controlled. There is, however, considerable divergence on the appropriate strategy. Harm is said to flow from pornography in two ways. First, it is theorized that there is a direct causal link between violent pornography and violence against women, so that such material can act as a trigger to aggression. Second, it is said that pornography contributes in a general way to myths about sexuality and about women that ultimately make violence and degradation more acceptable to society as a whole. According to this view, distinctions among types of pornography are invidious. Such material constitutes a continuum. It has been suggested that pornography represents and nourishes attitudes and activities inimical to the equality of men and women and that it presents demeaning images as normal and commendable, so that it perpetrates lies about aspects of women's humanity and denies the validity of their aspirations to be treated as full and equal citizens.

Osibajo and Fogam state that the conditions to be considered for a material to be classified as 'obscene' must show that the average person, applying contemporary community standards and viewing the material as a whole, would find that:

1. that the work appeals predominantly to "prurient" interest;
2. that it depicts or describes sexual conduct in a patently offensive way; and
3. that it lacks serious literary, artistic, political or scientific value.

The Nigeria pornography is trending, and pornography industries keeps growing particularly with the introduction of Nollywood. The pornographic movies accorded wanton acceptance and reception in the name of civility. The practice of sex today in Nigeria has been one of the most profitable acts in the film industries and that is not limited to Nigeria even the Europe and other countries. Currently, the Nigerian film produces 'blue films' Blue films or blue picture is a term used in Nigeria for an adult film, often made by amateurs or shot in a style recalling amateur pornography.

So many numbers of these films are now available and produced by the Nollywood industries. A website page titled 'pornography takes over Nollywood' has also gone viral and the page is hardly accessible and virus blocks the site because of great patronage.

27. Steven Kleinknecht, *Borders Conference – Rethinking the Line: The Canada–U.S. Border / Child Pornography on the Internet Session*, Research and Statistics Division, Department of Justice Canada, 2001.

28. The 1985 report of the Special Committee on Pornography and Prostitution (the Fraser), Committee <https://bdp.parl.ca/content/lop/researchpublications> (Accessed on May 24, 2023).

29 Y. Osibajo & K. Fogam, *Nigerian Media Law*. Lagos: Gravitas Publishments Ltd.

However, Nollywood films are turning into pornography industries that alone question the standard and moral aspects of the industry. Considering the fact that Nollywood has for long seem to portray the African culture and value in a celebrated context, but now the industry has changed its scope. The National Film and Video Censors Board (NFCVB) confiscated no fewer than 6,000 pornographic movies at major markets in Jos North and South Local Government Areas of Plateau.

With the advent of the internet and social media, it has become relatively easy to disseminate messages, information, news and pictures. The wide reach of the internet globally is such that whichever material is uploaded on it can be viewed or listened to across the entire continents of the world simply by the click of a computer mouse or by the use of devices such as mobile phones or tablets. In contemporary times, the internet has served as a tool for faster reach to targeted recipients of messages especially social media channels that allow for broadcast. Social media channels and the internet are tools that could be utilized to play both positive and negative roles in society.

In recent times, Nigerians have had to endure and confront a series of obscene displays of nudes and the sharing of sex tapes on the internet. While the morality and integrity of victims and those sharing such tapes may be subjected to public debate, it is essential that those involved in the act put the members of the public in consideration while flying such horror and indecent files on the internet as same is capable of causing damage on public decency and national morality.

Some people consider any depiction of nudity or sexual activity to be pornographic. What is objectionable, however, is not sexual content per se, or erotica, which depicts normal consensual sexual activity, but material in which one or more participants are demeaned, degraded, or abused in some manner. Pornography, according to this view, is material that condones or encourages sexual debasement. Such a distinction cuts across conventional definitions because it means that very explicit sexual depictions can be called erotica, while sexual material with relatively inexplicit but demeaning content can be called pornography. At the same time, much conventional pornography depicts naked women, and it is argued that such material perpetrates images of women as sexual objects and, thus,

30 'Sex, Nollywood and Nigerian Hypocrisy' available at thisisafrika.mellifestyle/sex-nollywood-and-nigeriahypocrisy/. Accessed on 28/2/2015.

31 Blue Films', Wikipedia.org/wiki/Blue-films/. (Accessed on 27th May, 2015).

32 Vanguard newspaper of June 22, 2107, 6,000 pornographic movies seized at just two areas in Jos <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2017/06/6000-pornographic-movies-seized-just-two-areas-jos/>

33 Sackson, M.. Computer Ethics: Are Students Concerned. First Annual Ethics Conference. Retrieved from Loyola University Chicago Web site <http://www.math.luc.edu/ethics96/papers/sackson.doc> 1996

can victimize women directly or indirectly. Indecent or obscene matters are those articles capable of corrupting public morality. They are articles which are likely to corrupt people who come in contact with them for instance children. It also includes articles that irritate or offends the mind of a right thinking individual. Such obscene materials include publication containing pornographic pictures and so on.

Law on Pornography in Nigeria

A cursory appraisal of the extant laws in Nigeria shows that the sharing of sex tapes, nudes and pornography on media is a grievous offence punishable with severe penalty under the Cybercrimes (Prevention and Prohibition) Act, the Criminal Code and the Penal Code.

Under the Cybercrimes Act, applicable in all states of the federation including FCT-Abuja, Section 24 of the Act provides thus;

(a) Any person who knowingly or intentionally sends a message or other matter by means of computer systems or network that is grossly offensive, pornographic or of an indecent, obscene or menacing character or causes any such message or matter to be so sent;... commits an offence under this Act and shall be liable on conviction to a fine of not more than N7, 000,000.00 or imprisonment for a term of not more than 3 years or to both such fine and imprisonment.

In Nigeria, the Criminal Code was initially the extant law regulating pornography publication. However, under the Criminal Code, the word pornography is not used but the words obscene publication by the use of articles. The Criminal Code empowers a constable possessed of a search warrant issued by a magistrate to enter into any premises and seize any article containing obscene publication and the magistrate who issued the search warrant or any magistrate may order the forfeiture of the obscene article. For the purpose of this subject matter, the word 'article' is defined by section 233B of the Code as anything capable of being or likely to be looked at and read or looked at or read and includes any film or record of a picture or pictures, and any sound records.

By virtue of section 233C (1) of the Criminal Code, an article shall be deemed to be obscene for the purposes of this Chapter if its effects taken as a whole is such as to tend to deprave and corrupt persons who are likely, having regard to all relevant circumstances, to read, see or hear the matter contained or embodied in it. Subsection 2 of this section extends obscene publication to any article of two or more distinct items the effect of any one of

³⁴ Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, Etc) Act, 2015

³⁵ Criminal Code, Cap C38 LFN 2004

³⁶ Penal Code Act, CAP 53 LFN 2004

which is such as to tend to deprave and corrupt. However, this does not apply to exhibitions in private houses to which the public are not admitted or to anything done in the course of television or sound broadcasting.

It is an offence under section 233D of the Criminal Code for a person to publish obscene material. The Section provides:

Subject to the provisions of this Chapter, any person who, whether for gain or not, distributes or projects any article deemed to be obscene for the purposes of this Chapter, commits an offence punishable on conviction by a fine not exceeding four hundred naira or by imprisonment for a term not exceeding three years or by both

It is however a defence under section 233F of the Criminal Code to prove that publication of the article in question is justified as being for the public good on the ground that it is in the interests of science, literature, art or learning or of other objects of general concern.

Furthermore, Section 170(B) of the Criminal Code Act provides:

Any person who knowingly sends, or attempts to send, by post anything which;
(b) encloses an indecent or obscene print, painting, photograph, lithograph, engraving, book, card, or article, or which has on it, or in it, or on its cover, any indecent, obscene, or grossly offensive words, marks, or designs; is guilty of a misdemeanour and is liable to imprisonment for one year.

Also the Penal Code provides that:

Whoever intentionally sends by post anything which-

- (a) encloses anything of such a nature as to be likely to cause injury to any person or thing in the course of conveyance; or*
- (b) encloses any obscene book, pamphlet, paper, gramophone record or similar article, drawing, painting, representation or figure, shall be punished with imprisonment for a term which may extend to one year or with fine or with both.*

It is noteworthy that the drafters of the Criminal Code and the Penal Code did not contemplate pornography as we have it today. At the time the two Codes were enacted, there was nothing like cybercrime and information technology as we have today. So, pornography from information and communication technology was not within contemplation.

From the analysis above, it is crystal clear that the sharing of indecent files on the internet or other related gadgets is an offence that the law frowns at. Apart from the personal injury

³⁷ Section 463 of the Penal Code

and effect on the victim, flying of same across the internet is equally capable of causing public nuisance which may result in the breach of public peace if handled lackadaisically. It is based on the above and other reasons that the federal legislature passed the Cybercrime Prohibition and Prevention Act which expressly makes mention of the word 'pornography.' Amongst other things, the Act provides an effective, unified and comprehensive legal, regulatory and institutional framework for the prohibition, prevention, detection, prosecution and punishment of cybercrimes and pornography in Nigeria. It deals with the protection of critical national information, infrastructure, and promotes cyber security and the protection of computer systems and networks, electronic communications, data and computer programs, intellectual property and privacy rights. It also deals with the issue of position of law on information and communication technology and pornographic items.

Law on Obscene Materials and Pornography in the United Kingdom

In the attempt to control and prevent wanton use of obscene material and pornography, over the years, the United Kingdom government has taken many steps. The steps include *inter alia*:

Children and Young Persons (Harmful Publications) Act 1955: This Act criminalises publishing articles consisting of stories told in pictures (whether or not accompanied by text) portraying crimes, violence, cruelty or incidents of a repulsive or horrible nature having a tendency to corrupt children. The maximum penalty is four months imprisonment and/or a £1,000 fine. The Attorney General's consent is needed to prosecute the offenders. The Obscene Publications Act criminalises the publication of an obscene article whether or not for gain. It also criminalises a person who has an obscene article for publication for gain (personal gain or gain for another).

Other measures include the punishment for the possession of an extreme pornographic image, contrary to the provision of the Criminal Justice and Immigration Act. Taking, making, distributing or publishing indecent images or pseudo-images of children, contrary to the Protection of Children Act; possession of an indecent image of a child, contrary to the provisions of the Criminal Justice Act; and possession of prohibited images of children, contrary to Coroners and Justice Act. Sending by means of a public electronic

38 *The Obscene Publications Act 1959*

39 *section 63 Criminal Justice and Immigration Act 2008*

40 *Section 1, Protection of Children Act 1978*

41 *Section 160 Criminal Justice Act 1988*

42 *Section 62 Coroners and Justice Act 2009*

communications network a message or other matter that is grossly offensive or of an indecent, obscene or menacing character, or false for the purpose of causing annoyance, inconvenience or needless anxiety to another, contrary to the provisions of Communications Act. In this regard, ssexual communication with a child which involves the use of obscene material, is covered by the provisions of the Sexual Offences Act that contains 2 years maximum imprisonment for the offenders and accomplices.

When considering whether the content of an article is “obscene”, prosecutors should distinguish between the content relating to criminal conduct (whether non-consensual activity, or consensual activity where serious harm is caused, or otherwise inextricably linked to criminality), which is likely to be obscene; Content relating to other non-criminal conduct, which is unlikely to be obscene, provided the audience is not young or otherwise vulnerable. One indicator that content is criminal in nature is if it is caught by the extreme pornography provisions.

Child Pornography

The Black's Law Dictionary defines child pornography as material depicting a person under the age of 18 engaged in sexual activity. The Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, Etc) Act, defines the term “child pornography” to include pornographic material that visually depicts ...

- (a) *a minor engaged in sexually explicit conduct;*
- (b) *a person appearing to be a minor engaged in sexually explicit conduct; and*
- (c) *realistic images representing a minor engaged in sexually explicit conduct.*

Child pornography is generally acknowledged to raise some issues that do not apply to pornography dealing exclusively with adults. Those issues have to do with the participation of children in the production of such material and their exposure to it. It is assumed that adults may choose to be involved in pornographic productions or to view them, while children are deemed incapable of giving informed consent to such activity. Accordingly, it is a general consensus that the use of children should be outlawed, and that any sexually explicit display involving children should be deemed obscene.

⁴³ Section 15A of the Sexual Offences Act 2003

⁴⁴ Jasmine V. Eggstein and Kenneth J. Knapp, *Fighting Child Pornography: A Review of Legal and Technological Developments*, vol 9 (4) *journal of digital forensics security and law*.

⁴⁵ Section 63 Criminal Justice and Immigration Act 2008

⁴⁶ Eighth Edition, Thomas Reuters, pg. 1349, 2014

⁴⁷ Section 23(4) of the Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, Etc) Act, 2015

In an attempt to curb this menace regionally, the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child prohibits the use of children in pornographic activities, performances and materials.

The Act defines the term “child” or “minor” to mean a person below 18 years of age and criminalise child pornography thus:

- (1) *Any person who intentionally uses any computer system or network in or for---*
- (a) *producing child pornography;*
 - (b) *offering or making available child pornography;*
 - (c) *distributing or transmitting child pornography;*
 - (d) *procuring child pornography for oneself or for another person;*

The Act further criminalise child pornography by providing for the offence of Child Pornography and other related offences, whose penalties range from 1 to 15 years imprisonment or fine ranging from N250,000.00 to N25,000,000.00.

- (e) *possessing child pornography in a computer system or on a computer data storage medium: commits an offence under this Act and shall be liable on conviction,*
- (I) *in the case of paragraphs (a),(b)and (c) to imprisonment for a term of 10 years or a fine of not more than N20,000,000.00 or to both fine and imprisonment; and*
- (ii) *in the case of paragraphs (d) and (e) of this subsection, to imprisonment for a term of not more than 5 years or a fine of not more than N10,000,000.00 or to both such fine and imprisonment.*

The main objectives of the Act as provided for in its section 1 are as follows:

- a) provide an effective and unified legal, regulatory and institutional framework for the prohibition, prevention, detection, prosecution and punishment of cybercrimes in Nigeria;*
- (b) ensure the protection of critical national information infrastructure; and*
- (c) promote cyber security and the protection of computer systems and networks, electronic communications, data and computer programs, intellectual property and privacy rights.*

Another Act of the parliament that is useful in this circumstance is the Child Right Act forbids the procurement of a child or the offer of a girl child for prostitution or for the production of Pornography and any pornographic performance. The Act provides that a child shall not be used. It further provides that a child shall not be procured or offered for

48 *African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child, Art. 27 (c).*

49 *Section 23(5)*

50 *Section 23(1)*

51 *Section 23*

52 *Section 30, The Child’s Right Act 2003, See also, The Child’s Right Law of Lagos State 2007 s 26. However, the Child Right Law only provides for prohibition of Child prostitution, leaving out Child pornography.*

prostitution or for the production of pornography or for any pornographic performance; The prescribed punishment for this offence is ten years imprisonment.

The problem with the pornography regulations is that the people in the anti-pornography movement always urge stricter legal prohibitions on “obscene” materials, even when viewed in private homes, and greater enforcement of existing laws, or both. It is to be noted that from history this conception has shown not to be sound and should not be adopted. The reason are as follows:

First, “obscene” pornography is difficult, if not impossible, to define satisfactorily under basic First Amendment principles. At most, it can be imprecisely limited to the ill-defined concept of “hard core” pornography, which might reach some of the online material criticized, but certainly not all of it. In particular, the current definition does not come close to reaching the materials that allegedly corrupt the moral tone of society, the health of relationships and family life, and the status of women. Second, any broader definition of obscenity would be inconsistent with basic First Amendment principles and could not be limited to sexually explicit materials in any principled way. It could easily pave the way for a radical curtailment of free expression across the board. What is more, enforcing such a sweeping suppression on what even adults may watch in the privacy of their homes would be impossible if we are to remain a free country.

Third, the history of Prohibition demonstrates the almost intractable difficulties of using legal coercion to deprive large segments of society of goods that they desire on moral grounds that they do not share. Censorship is another form of prohibition, which also has proved difficult to enforce even in authoritarian countries. Censorship of the Internet is especially difficult in free countries, although modern technologies are increasingly enabling authoritarian countries to control what their citizens view online.

Preventive Measures

In the United Kingdom, the government gives a new legal duty to the operators of online communication technology. Hence, significant steps have been taken to prevent the commission of the crime. The steps are as follows:

The online safety steps taken by the United Kingdom to prevent the abuse of the use of

⁵³ Section 30(2).

⁵⁴ Section 30(2)(e)

⁵⁵ Ezeanokwasa J. *Child Pornography under the Cybercrimes Act 2015 of Nigeria: The Law and its Challenges*, 4 *African Journal of Criminal Law and Jurisprudence*, 94-107, (2019).

⁵⁶ Jamie Rigg, *How the Digital Economy Act will come between you and porn*, 2017.

⁵⁷ Thomas C. Arthur, *The Problems With Pornography Regulation: Lessons From History*, <https://scholarlycommons.law.emory.edu/cgi> (Accessed on 24th June, 2023)

pornography materials include strengthening and requiring all websites that publish contents that are likely to be viewed as obscene to ensure their users are at least 18 years old. Age-verification technologies and third-party services are being used to qualify all users for access. This is necessary because it is too easy for children to access pornography online. An overview of the children who indulge in pornography describe their first viewing of online pornography as mostly unintentional.

The Office of Communications commonly known as Ofcom is given the government approval to regulate broadcasting, telecommunications and postal industries of the United Kingdom. Ofcom is an independent regulator, and it is given the powers to fine websites up to 10% of their annual worldwide turnover, or block their UK accessibility, if they fail to comply with the legislation. Bosses of such sites could also be held criminally liable if they fail to cooperate with Ofcom.

In the UK, online service providers, who publish or place pornographic content on their websites must put verifying measures to prevent children from accessing that content. This will capture commercial providers of pornography as well as sites that allow user-generated content. Any pornography site accessible to people in the UK will be subject to the same strict enforcement measures. Ofcom recommends the use of a growing range of age verification technologies available for companies to use that minimise the handling of users' data. All companies that use or build age verification technology are required to adhere to the UK's strong data protection regulations or face enforcement action from the Information Commissioner's Office. Also, the innovation in the AI-facial recognition space has been strong in recent years, with London-based online ID specialists Onfido that provide simple and secure identity verification solutions for digital access and is currently helping to solve the issue of verifying real people in the digital world.

In Nigeria, various measures are being adopted to ward off unwanted web content. These include the placement of notices in cyber-cafes prohibiting the browsing of sex sites and outright denial of service when customers or users are caught. The measure of prevention attainable by these means is very low. More will have to be done technically to guide against the circumvention of the restrictive measures earlier mentioned by smart users.

58 Jamie Rigg, "How the Digital Economy Act will come between you and porn. *engadget*. Retrieved 20 December 2017

59 Lunt, Peter; Livingstone, Sonia, *Regulating markets in the interest of consumers?: on the Changing Regime of Governance in the Financial Service and Communications Sectors. (PDF)*. Basingstoke, UK: Palgrave Macmillan. pp. 139–161, 2007.

The Internet Content Rating Association (ICRA) is an international, independent organization that empowers the public, especially parents, to make informed decisions about electronic media by means of the open and objective labeling of content. ICRA's dual aims are to protect children and youths from potentially harmful material, and to protect free speech on the Internet. There are two elements to the ICRA system: content labeling and filtering software.

- i. Web Filtering Software:* Web filtering programs seem to be the only known solution for now to the dangers of obscene web content applicable to private companies, ISPs, Cyber cafés, public libraries and in all computers used to access the Internet with a growing need to ensure that their computers are not being abused to access illegal or inappropriate materials. The use of valuable computer resources cannot be controlled unless a powerful set of monitoring and blocking tools are employed. Internet filter blocks SPAM email and pornographic images transmitted to a web browser or via email by residing between a company's or ISP's (Internet service provider) connection to the Internet via both incoming and outgoing network connections. It examines the contents and images of a web site and can determine whether the site displays what is commonly accepted as pornographic content.
- ii. Content Labeling:* Web authors fill in an online questionnaire describing the content of their site, simply in terms of what is and isn't present. ICRA then generates a Content Label (a short piece of computer code), which the author adds to his/her site. Users, especially parents of young children, cyber cafés etc. can then set their internet browser to allow or disallow access to web sites based on the objective information declared in the label and the subjective preferences of the user. ICRA's labeling system is designed to be as objective as possible, and to cover a wide range of content types.

In addition to this, it is imperative to understand that as Africans we hold morality and decency in high esteem and this generation of ours must act cautiously while using media and the internet in order to protect the integrity of our culture.

Conclusion

Although the problems of pornography has become a social and societal phenomenon which have assumed an alarming rate most importantly among the youth. The advent of computer and internet and electronic technology has added immensely to the problems. These gadgets have made it possible to transfer and share pornographic materials to millions of people by the touch of the button on the computer or phones. This has made it very difficult if not impossible to control pornographic activities among the populace. Tracking pornographic materials, arresting offender and securing evidence to proof the offence are daunting steps.

The passage of Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, Etc.) Act, is the right thing in the right direction. The Act provides the first platform upon which further and future legislation on the subject may be established. I am of the view that much still needs to be addressed by subsequent legislation on this subject matter.

Installation of Web Filtering Software: Web filtering programs seem to be the only known solution for now to the dangers of obscene web content applicable to private companies, ISPs, Cyber cafés, public libraries and in all computers used to access the Internet with a growing need to ensure that their computers are not being abused to access illegal or inappropriate materials. The use of valuable computer resources cannot be controlled unless a powerful set of monitoring and blocking tools are employed. Internet filter blocks SPAM email and pornographic images transmitted to a web browser or via e-mail by residing between a company's or ISP's (Internet service provider) connection to the Internet via both incoming and outgoing network connections. It examines the contents and images of a website and can determine whether the site displays what is commonly accepted as pornographic content.

References

1. Black's Law Dictionary, Eighth Edition at page 1349, 2014.
2. Concise Oxford Dictionary, 2014 Ed.
3. Section 1 of the English Obscene Publications Act of 1959
4. Adeyemi, A. A. "Obscene and Indecent Publications." In: T. O. Elias (Ed.). *Nigerian Press Law*. Edinburgh: University of Lagos and Evans Brothers Limited, 1969.
5. [1965] 1 All E.R. 1035, pp. 1038-1039
6. *Regina v. Hicklin* [1868] L.R. 3 QB 360 at 371 (Eng.)
7. Harry Kalven, Jr., *The Metaphysics of the Law of Obscenity*, SUP. CT. REV. 1, 5, 1960.
8. Gerard V. Bradley, Prolegomenon on Pornography, 41 HARV. J.L. & PUB. POL'Y 447, 447–56, 484–96 (2018).
9. Utah S. Concurrent Resolution on the Public Health Crisis, S.C.R. 9, 2016 Gen. Sess, 2016.
10. Itzin, C. Pornography Classified, 2003. <https://www.peacefire.org/censorware> (Accessed on 15th June, 2023).
11. Longe, O. B., & Longe, F. A. (2003). Health Risks Associated With IT Applications. Proceedings of the 14th Annual Conference of the Nigerian Computer Society.
12. Gail Dines, *Pornland: How Porn Has Hijacked Our Sexuality*, (2010).
13. Nat'l Ctr. on Sexual Exploitation, Pornography & Public Health: Research Summary 1, 2017.
14. Ronald Weitzer, *Pornography's Effects: The Need for Solid Evidence*, 17 Violence Against Women, 667–75, 2011.
15. Ronald Weitzer, *Opinion, This Look at Porn Was Biased*, Wash. Post, 2016. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/opinions/this-look-at-porn-was-biased/>.
16. Matthew LaPlante, *In Utah, The Fight Against Porn Is Increasingly Being Framed as a Public Health Crisis*, Wash. Post, 2018,
17. Amber Phillips, *Porn Has Been Declared a 'Public Health Crisis' in Utah. Here's Why*. Wash. Post 2016.
18. Melinda Wenner Moyer, *The Sunny Side of Smut*, SCI. AM. 2011, <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/the-sunny-side-of-smut/>
19. Mireille Miller-Young, *Porn Isn't a Public Health Hazard. It's a Scapegoat.*, Wash. Post, pp67-89 2016. <http://www.washingtonpost.com/news/in-theory>
20. Ronald Weitzer, *Opinion, This Look at Porn Was Biased*, Wash. Post 2016. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/opinions/this-look-at-porn-was-biased/>
21. Rubén de Alarcón et al., *Online Porn Addiction: What We Know and What We Don't—A Systematic Review*, J. CLINICAL MED., 15 Jan. 2019, at 1, 11–12.
22. Steven Kleinknecht, —[Borders Conference Rethinking the Line: The CanadaU.S. Border / Child](#)

- [Pornography on the Internet Session](#), Research and Statistics Division, Department of Justice Canada, 2001.
23. The 1985 report of the Special Committee on Pornography and Prostitution (the Fraser), Committee <https://bdp.parl.ca/content/lop/researchpublications> (Accessed on May 24, 2023).
 24. Y. Osibajo & K. Fogam, *Nigerian Media Law*. Lagos: Gravitas Publishments Ltd.
 25. Blue Films', [Wikipedia.org/wiki/Blue_films/](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Blue_films/). (Accessed on 27th May, 2015).
 26. Vanguard newspaper of June 22, 2107, 6,000 pornographic movies seized at just two areas in Jos <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2017/06/6000-pornographic-movies-seized-just-two-areas-jos/>
 27. Sackson, M.. Computer Ethics: Are Students Concerned. First Annual Ethics Conference. Retrieved from Loyola University Chicago Web site <http://www.math.luc.edu/ethics96/papers/sackson.doc> 1996
 28. Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, Etc) Act, 2015
 29. Criminal Code, Cap C38 LFN 2004
 30. Penal Code Act, CAP 53 LFN 2004
 31. The Obscene Publications Act 1959
 32. Criminal Justice Act 1988
 33. Coroners and Justice Act 2009
 34. Sexual Offences Act 2003
 35. Jasmine V. Eggstein and Kenneth J. Knapp, *Fighting Child Pornography: A Review of Legal and Technological Developments*, vol 9 (4) journal of digital forensics security and law.
 36. Criminal Justice and Immigration Act 2008
 37. Eighth Edition, Thomas Reuters, pg. 1349, 2014
 38. Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, Etc) Act, 2015
 39. African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child, Art. 27 (c).
 40. The Child's Right Act 2003
 41. Ezeanokwasa J. *Child Pornography under the Cybercrimes Act 2015 of Nigeria: The Law and its Challenges*, 4 African Journal of Criminal Law and Jurisprudence, 94-107, 2019.
 42. Jamie Rigg, How the Digital Economy Act will come between you and porn, 2017.
 43. Thomas C. Arthur, The Problems With Pornography Regulation: Lessons From History, <https://scholarlycommons.law.emory.edu/cgi> (Accessed on 24th June, 2023)
 44. Jamie Rigg, "How the Digital Economy Act will come between you and porn. *engadget*. Retrieved 20 December 2017

45. *Lunt, Peter; Livingstone, Sonia, Regulating markets in the interest of consumers?: on the Changing Regime of Governance in the Financial Service and Communications Sectors. (PDF). Basingstoke, UK: Palgrave Macmillan. pp. 139–161, 2007.*